

Heterocyclic Fungicides. Part-III

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4-Monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one and acetoacetic ester in ethanol give a product which on condensation with phenyl hydrazine, hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide hydrochloride and 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine yields 4,4'-bis-2-pyrazolin-5-ones with mixed nuclei, which are oxidised with a solution of iodine or with nitric acid to the corresponding pyrazole derivatives. 9 Compounds thus prepared were screened for antifungal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia Oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium Oryzae*.

IN our previous work¹⁻⁶ on the heterocyclic five membered compounds, we have reported significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia Oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium Oryzae* of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones. It encouraged us to extend our investigation to other pyrazolone derivatives. In this investigation 4,4'-bis-2-pyrazolin-5-ones and their oxidation products have been synthesised as outlined below :

R = C₆H₅

R₁ = Ph, H, NH₂C O (Hydrochloride), 2,4-DNP

4-Monobromo-2-pyrazolin-5-one when condensed with acetoacetic ester in presence of ethanol affords the 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-5-one (1), which displayed significant activity. Further phenyl hydrazine, hydrazine hydrate, semicarbazide hydrochloride and 2,4-dinitro phenyl hydrazine have been condensed with the ester group at C₄-position of 2-pyrazolin-5-one to form substituted 2-pyrazolin-5-one, in which the

2-pyrazolin-5-one nuclei were linked together at C₄ position by a carbon-carbon single bond. The bis compound has been reported earlier⁷. Its identity has been established by the super-imposition of the IR absorption spectra.

The oxidation of the above bis-compound resulting in the conversion of was accomplished by the

treatment of alkaline solution of the 4, 4'-bis-2-pyrazoline-5-one with a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide. The same oxidation product could be obtained in an alternate method in which the bis-compound was treated with (1:1) HNO₃.

It has been prepared by a method reported earlier⁸. Its identity has been established by the super imposition of the IR absorption spectra.

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 206 nm < (log ε = 4.6749), 246 nm < (log ε = 4.5794) and NMR(CCl₄) δ 2.03(S,3H), 2.43(S,3H).

All these compounds prepared during the present investigation have been assayed for antifungal activity against *P. Oryzae* and *H. Oryzae* using spore germination test at various concentration by the standard method⁹. It was observed that compounds No. 7 and 8 did not exhibit significant activity while the remaining compounds showed high activity against the pathogen *P. Oryzae*. Cpd. No.2 and 5 cause 100% inhibition of *P. Oryzae* spore at 1000 ppm concentration. Highest activity was exhibited by Cpd. No. 5, which inhibited 90% of *P. Oryzae* spore germination at 250 ppm concentration. Cpd. No. 1, 2, 6, 7, 8 and 9 did not exhibit significant fungicidal activity against the pathogen *H. Oryzae* while the remaining Cpd. No. 3,

4 and 5 showed significant activity. Cpd. No. 3 causes 70% inhibition of *H. Oryzae* spore at 1000 ppm concentration. It was concluded from our observation on fungicidal activities of the prepared compounds (Table-3) that oxidation of the bis-derivatives resulting in the creation of new linkage

Experimental

The m.p. and analytical values of the compounds prepared are listed in Table (1-2). The I.R. spectra, NMR spectra and UV data are given in the experiments.

heated for 1 hr. on a water bath, cooled and the resulting mixture was added to it. The product was crystallised from ethanol, Yield 80%,
IR (cm⁻¹): 1595 (ring C=O) presence of enolic band.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-(2'-pyrazolin-3'-methyl-5'-one-4'-yl)-5-one :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) and 80% hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mole) were taken and refluxed in slow flame for 2 hrs and kept it for overnight, no solid was obtained. Added dil.HCl to it. A cream colour compound was obtained.

TABLE—1 4,4'-bis-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONES

Cpd. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	M.P. °C.	Calc./ (Found)%		
					C	H	N
2.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	320 (d)	69.36 (69.46)	5.20 (5.33)	16.18 (16.09)
3.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	306	62.22 (62.18)	5.18 (5.14)	20.74 (20.68)
4.	C ₆ H ₅	CONH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃	305	57.50 (57.53)	4.79 (4.81)	22.36 (22.40)
5.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₆	185	55.04 (55.12)	3.66 (3.62)	19.26 (19.31)

TABLE—2 PYRAZOLE BLUE COMPOUNDS

Cpd. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	M.P. °C.	Calc./ (Found)%		
					C	H	N
6.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	230	69.76 (69.70)	4.65 (4.55)	16.27 (16.17)
7.	C ₆ H ₅	H	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂	199	62.68 (62.59)	4.47 (4.57)	20.89 (20.78)
8.	C ₆ H ₅	CONH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃	228	57.87 (57.85)	4.18 (4.21)	22.50 (22.47)
9.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ (NO ₂) ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₆	148	55.29 (55.31)	3.22 (3.24)	19.35 (19.41)

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one : (Cpd.No.1)

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-monobromo-5-pyrazolone (0.01 mole) and acetoacetic ester (0.01 mole) were taken in ethanol and refluxed on water bath for 8 hrs. evaporated the excess of ethanol, cooled and added water to it. An yellowish brown compound was isolated and crystallised from ethanol. M.P. 158-160°, gives red colouration with ethanolic FeCl₃, soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gives positive test for ester group. (Found C, 63.61 ; H, 5.99 ; N, 9.24 ; C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₄ requires C, 63.57 ; H, 5.96 ; N, 9.27%).

4,4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) was dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid and phenyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) was added to it and was

crystallised from ethanol, gives colouration with FeCl₃ and soluble in 10% alkali.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-4-(1'-amido-2'-pyrazolin-3'-methyl-5'-one-4'-yl)-5-one :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(1' acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl)-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) was dissolved in ethanol. Semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.01 mole) and sodium acetate (0.02 mole) were taken and dissolved in minimum quantity of water. The ethanolic solution was added to this aqueous solution, refluxed for 2 hrs on water bath and cooled. A white crystalline compound separated, it was filtered, washed with water for 2 to 3 times and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ and is soluble in 10% NaOH solution.

TABLE—3 TOXICITY OF THE COMPOUNDS AGAINST *P. Oryzae* AND (*H. Oryzae*) SPORE GERMINATION

Cpd. No.	% inhibition over control concentration (ppm)				
	62.5	125	250	500	1000
1.	35 (23)	43 (34)	64 (43)	77 (50)	87 (57)
2.	40 (10)	60 (18)	75 (29)	90 (40)	100 (55)
3.	34 (31)	46 (41)	60 (50)	70 (62)	94 (70)
4.	25 (20)	40 (31)	52 (46)	74 (52)	85 (65)
5.	56 (28)	78 (44)	90 (52)	100 (56)	100 (68)
6.	34 (14)	49 (18)	55 (26)	65 (36)	72 (56)
7.	5 (3)	20 (12)	25 (22)	35 (31)	45 (40)
8.	18 (8)	25 (14)	35 (25)	42 (29)	52 (46)
9.	20 (18)	27 (28)	38 (30)	52 (38)	60 (46)

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-[1'-(2,4-dinitrophenyl) 2'-pyrazolin-3'-methyl-5'-one-4'-yl]-5-one :

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(1'-acetyl-1'-carboethoxy methyl) 2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole) and 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine (0.01 mole) were taken in acetic acid and refluxed for 2 hrs in a slow flame, cooled and added water to it. An yellowish compound thus separated, was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, gives colouration with alcoholic FeCl_3 , soluble in 10% NaOH solution.

Preparation of oxidation product of 4,4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) :

Method-I : 4,4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) (2 g) dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.). A saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (25 ml) was added to it with constant stirring. A blue coloured compound thus obtained was filtered, washed with 10% solution of sodium thiosulphate (15 ml). Crystallised from acetone as blue coloured crystals,

m.p. 230°, yield 75%. IR-1695 cm^{-1} (ring $\text{C}=\text{O}$),

enolic band absent. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 206nm < (log $\epsilon=4.6749$), 246nm < (log $\epsilon=4.5794$) NMR (CCl_4) δ 2.03 (S, 3H), 2.43 (S, 3H).

Method-II : 4,4'-bis-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one) (1 g) was taken. To it (1 : 1) HNO_3 (5 ml) was added. Immediate formation of a blue pasty mass which converted into blue solids after few minutes. The compound was filtered, washed with aqueous 10% NaOH (10 ml). On crystallisation from acetone gives blue crystals, m.p. 230°, yield 80%.

The compound was insoluble in 10% aqueous NaOH and did not give colouration with alcoholic

FeCl_3 . IR-1695 cm^{-1} (ring $\text{C}=\text{O}$), enolic band absent. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 206 nm < (log $\epsilon=4.6749$), 246 nm < (log $\epsilon=4.5794$) NMR (CCl_4) δ 2.03 (S, 3H), 2.43 (S, 3H)

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